

D14.2 Communication Materials

Electrochemical
oxidation of cyclic
and biogenic
substrates for high
efficiency production
of organic chemicals

ELOXYCHEM

eloxychem-horizon.eu
HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01
1st January 2024 - 30th June 2028

Funded by
the European Union

Document control sheet

Project	ELOXYCHEM - Electrochemical oxidation of cyclic and biogenic substrates for high efficiency production of organic chemicals
Grant Agreement n°	101138376
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Coordinator	SINTEF
Project start date	1 January 2024
Project duration	54 months
Work package n° and title	14 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation (RP1)
Work package leader	ETA
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Lead Beneficiary	ETA
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Reviewer(s)	Theresa Rücker, Bernd Wittgens
Review date	24 June 2024
Due Date	30 June 2024

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1. Introduction

This document is the comprehensive communication guide for ELOXYCHEM, ensuring consistent use of brand elements across all channels to effectively represent the project.

ELOXYCHEM's visual identity serves as a recognizable tool for presenting the project at events, conferences, workshops, and other activities to the European Commission, the scientific community, industrial entities, and the general public. It includes logos for different backgrounds, fonts, a color palette, graphic elements, and templates for project presentations, documents, posters, leaflets, and the website.

2. Project Logo and Graphic Elements

The **project logo** features two wires with sockets forming a hexagonal shape, referring to a cyclohexane/cyclohexene - a representative of the cyclic alkane/alkene family and representing electricity as a renewable energy carrier. The lettering mimics an electrical circuit, modernized for a contemporary look. The blue and orange colors reflect the electrical theme.

ELOXYCHEM

Figure 1 - Official ELOXYCHEM logos on different screens

This colour palette ensures a consistent visual identity, creating a pleasant and user-friendly interface.

Fonts

Archivo

Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 012345678
(.,:;-+**#|!^E\$%&/?^g@)!*=>?<±¶%‰×†•€

Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 012345678
(.,:;-+**#|!^E\$%&/?^g@)!*=>?<±¶%‰×†•€

Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 012345678
(.,:;-+**#|!^E\$%&/?^g@)!*=>?<±¶%‰×†•€

Colors

R: 13
G: 0
B: 147
#0D0093

C: 100
M: 93
Y: 20
K: 70

R: 255
G: 53
B: 0
#FF3500

C: 0
M: 90
Y: 100
K: 0

Figure 2 – ELOXYCHEM colours palette and fonts

Figure 3 – ELOXYCHEM graphic elements

3. Templates

As the elaboration of the logo and colors palette have been completed, a series of templates have been designed in compliance with the visual identity and made available to all partners on the project shared area - “*Shared Point*” managed by SINTEF. The templates include:

- Presentation slides (ppt)
- Minutes of meeting (word doc)
- Deliverable report (word doc)

Figure 4 - ELOXYCHEM slides template

Figure 5 - ELOXYCHEM minutes of meeting

Figure 6 - ELOXYCHEM deliverable template

The project

ELOXYCHEM - EElectrochemical oxidation of cYclic and biogenic substrates for high efficiency production of organic CHEMicals is a Horizon Europe project that aims to replace existing chemicals process developing a new electrochemical conversion platform and drop-in technology.

The project started in January 2024 2024 and wi continue through 30 June 2026.

Consortium

Coordinator

Partners

Greening the chemical industry with electricity

ELOXYCHEM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101138376, call: HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-Q1

 ELOXYCHEM Project
 eloxychem-horizon.eu
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Figure 7 - ELOXYCHEM leaflet (p.1)

Figure 8 - ELOXYCHEM leaflet (p.2)

4. Website

ELOXYCHEM website is the main digital hub of the project during its lifetime and beyond. To ensure the project's best visibility, the website is accessible with an intuitive URL: <https://www.eloxychem-horizon.eu/>

The ELOXYCHEM website has been developed in line with the project characteristics and follows this structure:

Figure 9 - ELOXYCHEM website structure

Figure 10 - ELOXYCHEM Homepage (<https://www.eloxychem-horizon.eu/>)

5. Social media channels

ELOXYCHEM's social media channels will actively promote key messages to target stakeholders. In the project's initial phase, these channels will focus on raising awareness and facilitating collaboration with stakeholders and related initiatives.

LinkedIn will serve as the primary platform to build a broad audience of interested entities, promoting participation in and organization of research activities, events, and workshops.

Figure 11 - [ELOXYCHEM LinkedIn page](#)

The LinkedIn post should follow this format as demonstrated below, with the following project relevant ‘#’ and ‘tags’.

[TEXT]
[Link]
[Image]

Partners: [SINTEF](#) | [SINTEF Industry](#) | [Max Planck Institute](#) | [Evonik](#) | [IDENER.AI](#) | [ETA Florence Renewable Energies](#) | [Z Prime](#) | [MEGARA RESINS](#) | [ESy-Labs GmbH](#) | [IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY & MEDICINE](#) | [Iconiq Innovation](#)

[Processes4Planet Partnership](#) | [A.SPIRE](#) | [CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#)

[#ELOXYCHEM](#) [#greenchemistry](#) [#electrochemicaloxidation](#) [#DDDA](#) [#digitalcontrol](#) [#renewableenergy](#) [#energy](#) [#unsaturatedfattyacids](#) [#pilotplant](#) [#horizoneurope](#) [#organicchemicals](#) [#greendeal](#) [#repowereu](#) [#twintransition](#) [#greentransition](#) [#digitaltransition](#)

YouTube will be used as repository for ELOXYCHEM videos, the project YouTube channel can be accessed here <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqDXD8clewO-ePdnzen1BzQ> and/or using the tag @ELOXYCHEM.

Figure 12 - [ELOXYCHEM YouTube Page](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqDXD8clewO-ePdnzen1BzQ)

6. Conclusion

By M6, the initial dissemination and communication materials, along with the digital tools, will be completed and operational. These resources will be distributed to Consortium partners and made available in the project's website member area. Future updates and additions will be documented in subsequent versions of this deliverable. These tools are essential for implementing the Plan for Dissemination and Communication (D14.1), which outlines the key project messages, target audiences, and planned actions to actively promote the project and publicly share its results.

7. Partners

